

Design and Implementation of a Real-Time Computer Vision Weapons

Detection System

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Abstract:

The purpose of this project was to determine if there was a way to leverage machine learning with image recognition to build a weapons detection system that could be used at schools to identify potential threats and notify authorities in real-time in order to improve school security. The weapons detection system was built using Python as the base code with integrations to Ultralytics YOLOv8n deep learning model to execute image recognition and OpenCV image capture. An open source gun dataset was used to train the weapons image library, and Twilio was used to send alerts. The weapons detection system was able to consistently capture guns with confidence scores ranging from .70 to .90.

Introduction:

“Lock, Lights, Out of Sight!” This phrase has become all too familiar in American high schools. Each month, schools across America are required to conduct lockdown drills in case of an active assailant. But why have these drills become part of the national student body routine? Why are students trained for an event that should never occur in the first place? What solutions need to be introduced for improvement? Since the Columbine High School shooting in 1999, there have been 844 school shootings in the United States.

As a result of these tragedies, 1,146 people have been injured, with 540 total fatalities (Ballotpedia, 2024). For perspective, every student who passed away in these school shootings could have sat in about 9 school buses.

But schools have precautions to prevent this in the future, right? Although U.S. schools believe that lockdown practices prepare students for a possible emergency, The Juvenile Justice Information Exchange, a leading adolescent data reporter based at Kennesaw State University, concludes that “There's almost no research that confirms the value of these shooter drills either for preventing school shootings or for protecting the school community” (Rodriguez, 2023). In addition, most schools in the U.S. rely on security cameras that are entirely passive. This requires security personnel to monitor security cameras every second; often missing a threat or responding after it's too late. While School Resource Officers add another layer of security, they can't be everywhere on campus at once, and hiring additional security is expensive.

This leads to my question: Leveraging machine learning with image recognition and Python coding (including capitalizing on third-party APIs), is there a way to build a weapons detection system that can be used at schools to identify potential threats and notify authorities in real-time in order to improve school security?

Materials:

To develop a real-time weapons detection system capable of identifying weapons, several hardware and software pieces are required. Each of the materials leveraged were selected to support image recognition, model training, live video processing, and image storage.

I. Hardware

A. Windows Computer

The hardware used included a Windows 11 PC equipped with an NVIDIA 30, 40, or 50 series GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) that supports CUDA (Compute Unified Device Architecture). Figure 1 below displays the hardware specifications of the PC used to train and run the weapons detection model:

System Hardware Specifications
CPU: AMD Ryzen 7 7800X3D
GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 SUPER
RAM: 32GB DDR5 6000MHz CL32
Storage: 2TB NVMe SSD

Figure 1 - System Hardware Specifications

B. Webcam

A 4K 60fps USB-A webcam was used to provide a high resolution live video feed for object detection. Specifically, the Insta360 Link 2C was used.

C. Computer Monitor

A computer monitor with HDMI or DisplayPort connections was used to allow users to view detections in real-time.

D. Server

A server is required as a place to store/save detected weapons images and assign an HTTP address/URL.

II. Software

A. Python Programming Language

Python version 3.10 was the primary software/code used for developing the system. Figure 2 shows the exact version of Python used from Python.org:

Python 3.10.0	Oct. 4, 2021
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Figure 2 - Python Version

B. YOLOv8n Deep Learning Model

To execute image recognition, a YOLOv8n (You Only Look Once) deep learning model was selected.

C. OpenCV Image Capture

The final piece of software used was OpenCV for image capturing. OpenCV is a software that can screenshot frames from live video feeds.

III. Weapons Image Libraries

For the YOLOv8n deep learning model to be effective at detecting weapons it requires a large dataset of weapon images.

IV. Communication Services

To communicate quickly with a School Resource Officer (SRO) or security personnel, the weapons detection system had to send an alert immediately after detecting a weapon. To accomplish this, a third party SMS (Short Message Service) API was necessary. For this weapons detection system, Twilio was selected as the preferred messaging service.

Methods:

I. System Architecture Overview

To develop a real-time weapons detection system capable of identifying weapons requires special hardware, software and third-party communications systems. Each of the materials leveraged were selected to support image recognition model training, live video processing, and image storage. Figure 3 visualizes the system architecture overview that was built.

Figure 3 - System Architecture Overview

II. Hardware

A. Windows Computer

The hardware used included a Windows 11 PC equipped with an NVIDIA 30, 40, or 50 series GPU (Graphics Processing Unit). These GPUs support CUDA (Compute Unified Device Architecture), which enables accelerated processing required for training deep learning models. CUDA allows the GPU to process large amounts of image data simultaneously, which ultimately reduces model training time and real-time training latency.

B. Webcam

A 4K 60fps USB-A webcam was used to provide a high resolution live video feed for object detection. Specifically, the Insta360 Link 2C was used.

A 4K resolution (3840 x 2160 pixels) webcam was chosen because it offers four times the pixel definition of a standard 1080p webcam (1920 x 1080 pixels), which makes it ideal for picking up specific details at far distances, such as objects at the end of a hallway or room. The webcam was 60 frames per second (fps) also, as higher frames rates such as 120 or 240 require significantly more processing power. This additional computational demand could have reduced the performance of the deep learning model, making 60fps the optimal balance between smoothness and system efficiency.

C. Computer Monitor

Finally, a computer monitor with HDMI or DisplayPort connections was used to allow users to view detections in real-time.

III. Software

A. Python Programming Language

The primary software/code used in developing the system was the programming language. In order to effectively code the weapons detection system, Python version 3.10 was downloaded onto the Windows computer. Python was selected over other programming languages, such as Java, C#, or C++, because it provides extensive support for machine learning and deep learning models. Additionally, Python allows for seamless integrations of different pieces of the system, including the deep learning model, detected weapons image storage, and SMS alert mechanism.

B. YOLOv8n Deep Learning Model

The backbone of the weapons detection system is the deep learning model. For the sake of image recognition, a YOLOv8n (You Only Look Once) deep learning model was selected. YOLO models are popularly used in image recognition applications because of their ability to detect objects in real-time while maintaining a high accuracy. YOLOv8n was specifically selected because it has fast inference speeds, while still maintaining a high accuracy. Unlike traditional image recognition software, YOLO can draw bounding boxes around detected objects. This feature makes YOLO models particularly desirable for weapons detection so a human observer can quickly decipher whether or not a weapon has accurately been detected.

The YOLOv8n model was imported through the Ultralytics Python package in the Windows Command Prompt. After

installing Ultralytics, the model was imported directly into the Python environment. Figure 4 shows the command used to install the Ultralytics package, along with the Python code used to import the YOLOv8n model into the environment.


```
YOLOv8n Model Import Example

The following Python code installs the Ultralytics package and imports the YOLOv8n model:

pip install ultralytics

from ultralytics import YOLO
model = YOLO('yolov8n.pt')
```

Figure 4 - YOLOv8n Model Import Code

C. OpenCV Image Capture & Storage

The final piece of software used was OpenCV for image capturing. OpenCV is a software that can screenshot frames from live video feeds. This capability was essential for the weapons detection system, which needed to save photos of detected weapons to a server so Twilio could retrieve the photo using Python code and send an alert with a link to the detection. Figure 5 shows the command used to install OpenCV into the environment, along with basic code used to initialize the camera.


```
OpenCV Camera Initialization Example

The following Python code installs OpenCV and initialize a webcam feed:

pip install opencv-python

import cv2
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
ret, frame = cap.read()
```

Figure 5 - OpenCV Camera Initialization Code

IV. Weapons Image Libraries

For the deep learning model to be effective at detecting weapons it was trained on a large dataset of weapon images. This made sourcing or creating a weapons image library essential. When selecting images for the dataset, weapons from a wide variety of angles were included. Because security cameras are stationary, the model had to be able to recognize weapons from a wide variety of angles, distances, and lighting conditions. This is especially important in schools, where threats don't always appear in predictable ways. Training the model on a wide variety of images also improved final detection accuracy, and ensured maximum security in a real world school environment.

V. Twilio SMS API / Communication Services

In order to communicate quickly with a School Resource Officer (SRO) or security personnel, the weapons detection system had to send an alert immediately after detecting a weapon. To accomplish this, a third party SMS (Short Message Service) API was necessary. For this weapons detection system, Twilio was selected as the preferred messaging service.

Twilio provides SMS services to major companies such as Uber, Airbnb, Netflix, Shopify, Salesforce, Yelp, and Doordash, showing its potential scalability to multiple phone numbers. The first step in implementing Twilio was creating a Twilio account. Once the account was created, an account SID, authentication token, and Twilio phone number were provided. These credentials then were integrated into the Python environment. When a weapon detection occurs, Twilio sends an SMS message to a designated security personnel, or School Resource Officer's phone number, which was also configured in the Python

code. Figure 6 shows the Python code to import Twilio into the environment:

```
from twilio.rest import Client

ACCOUNT_SID = ""
AUTH_TOKEN = ""

TWILIO_NUMBER = ""
TARGET_NUMBER = ""

client = Client(ACCOUNT_SID, AUTH_TOKEN)

message = client.messages.create(
    body="",
    from_=TWILIO_NUMBER,
    to=TARGET_NUMBER
```

Figure 6 - Twilio Python Code

VI: Image Library Collection, Bounding Box Annotation, and Processing

Before training the YOLOv8n deep learning model, images within the dataset require bounding box annotations. Bounding boxes are rectangular coordinates placed around an object in an image, which allows the deep learning model to learn both the location and the classification of the object. Each bounding box includes coordinate values and an associated class label, ex “gun”, “spoon”, “banana”, “wine-glass”. This information is used during training to teach the model how to identify weapons.

Creating bounding box annotations manually requires annotation tools such as Roboflow, where each weapon in the dataset must be labeled individually. Because this process typically requires several thousand manual annotations, finding an existing labeled dataset was sourced through an independent passion project found online. The publisher of the article created the gun library by collecting 5000 images from The Internet Movie Firearms Database (IMFDB), a community-built Wiki that documents the guns found in movies, television series, video games, and anime. This sourced dataset already had bounding

box annotations, which allowed the manual annotation step to be skipped. Figure 7 displays multiple bounding box annotations:

Figure 7 - Bounding Box Annotations

However, the dataset included multiple different images with different annotations, ex “rifle”, “shotgun”, “pistol”. Because the goal of the weapons detection system was to detect guns broadly, preprocessing was required. Python code was written to go through each of the annotated images and convert all firearm categories into the single label “gun”. Figure 8 shows the Python code used in the label preprocessing step:

```

x, y = xmin + bw/2, ymin + bh/2
return x/w, y/h, bw/w, bh/h

def parse_voc(xml_path):
    root = ET.parse(xml_path).getroot()
    w = int(root.find("size/width").text)
    h = int(root.find("size/height").text)

    labels = []
    for obj in root.findall("object"):
        b = obj.find("bndbox")
        x,y,bw,bh = voc_to_yolo(
            w,h,
            int(b.find("xmin").text),
            int(b.find("ymin").text),
            int(b.find("xmax").text),
            int(b.find("ymax").text)
        )
        labels.append(f"0 {x:.6f} {y:.6f} {bw:.6f} {bh:.6f}") # class 0 = gun

    return labels

```

Figure 8 - Preprocessing Python Code

VII. Training Procedure

After preprocessing the dataset, the YOLOv8n deep learning model was trained using the 5000 labeled gun images. Training was performed over 100 epochs (iterations), which allowed the model to repeatedly analyze the dataset and improve over time. During each epoch, the model processed all of the training images, compared its predicted bounding boxes to the actual bounding boxes in the dataset, and adjusted its parameters.

The model training was completed using a Windows 11 PC equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 4070 Super GPU that supports CUDA acceleration. GPU acceleration significantly reduced the training time, allowing the YOLOv8n model, built on top of the PyTorch deep learning framework, to complete training in just under 2 hours. After completing 100 epochs, the final detection accuracy of the model reached approximately 83%. All training result data were then saved to a local folder on the Windows PC for review. The trained model was then integrated into the live detection system using Python code. Figure 9 displays the final detection accuracy after training.

Figure 9 - Final Detection Accuracy

Figure 10

End-to-End Process Summary:

The detection process follows a sequential pipeline to achieve real-time weapons detection. First, cameras capture live activity around the school campus. The live video feed is then processed by the YOLOv8n deep learning model, and analyzes each frame to detect potential weapons.

When the YOLO model detects a weapon, Python code takes a screenshot of the detected frame. The image is then sent to a local HTTP server, where Python code saves it for access and storage.

After the image is stored, Python code initiates the Twilio API, which sends an alert and a link of the detected image to the predefined phone number(s). Finally a phone alert is delivered to security personnel or the School Resource Officer. Figure 10 visualizes the pipeline.

Analysis:

I. Response Time Metrics

The weapons detection system completed the full process of identifying a weapon, saving the image to the server, and initiating and sending the SMS message via Twilio in 2-5 seconds.

II. Accuracy Rates

When testing real guns at different angles, within 5-10 feet of the camera, the weapons detection system model yielded confidence scores ranging from .70 to .90.

III. False Positives

Some false positives were detected (i.e. an object that was not a gun was detected to be a gun).

IV. Limited Testing

Testing with real guns was limited to three. Additional testing was done on high-definition gun images printed on a white background.

V. Image Library

Many of the gun images that were trained from the image library, contained medium to large images close to medium distance images. These images are easier to train and, ultimately, detect, compared to images that were taken further away.

VI. Image Distance

Guns, and images of guns, were tested at a distance of only 5 - 10 feet from the camera.

VII. Negative Examples

No negative examples were trained and added to the model. Negative images are images that the weapons detection system might mistake as a gun. Without training the system on negative images, confidence scores are not as high as possible and there are increased false positives.

VIII. Performance Comparison: Traditional Security vs AI Weapons/Image Detection

According to a March 2015 article by Donald et al. in *Applied Ergonomics, Work Exposure and Vigilance Decrements In Closed Circuit Television Surveillance*, “After 12 min of continuous video monitoring an operator is likely to miss up to 45% of screen activity and after 22 min of

viewing up to 95% of activity is overlooked (Donald et al., 2015). Comparatively, AI can watch every frame and well trained models can detect close to 90% of events.

IX. Real-world Deployment Challenges

In schools, models must be trained on smaller images of guns, so the system can recognize an image from 25 - 75 meters away. Additionally, many schools have low-resolution cameras.

Discussion:

A weapons detection system was effectively built leveraging machine learning with image recognition and Python coding, including leveraging 3rd party APIs. This system can be implemented at schools to identify potential threats and notify authorities in real-time in order to improve school security. The ideal solution includes human monitoring in combination with a weapons detection system. Opportunities also extend beyond the use for school security, as a weapons detection system could be implemented and save lives in many more areas including concerts, sporting events and political events. For outdoor events, drones with cameras would be the ideal vehicle.

Conclusion and Future Steps:

Based on the prototype developed, a production-grade, real-time weapons detection system can be developed using machine learning, image recognition, and Python. This system would be capable of identifying potential threats on school

grounds and alerting authorities in real-time, thereby improving school security at reasonable cost. AI can monitor every frame continuously and alert authorities to potential threats that humans miss, thus, saving more lives. Models should be trained to the surrounding environment and kept to a manageable false-positive rate.

Future steps for a production-grade system are enhancing and optimizing the image library and training model (smaller images for distance) and training the model on non-guns to avoid false positives.

Finally, activating the detection system with drones offers additional opportunities.

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